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**A Sensitivity Analysis of PSO Parameters - P2P Electricity Market
Problem Case Study**

Ricardo Faia and Miguel Vieira
GECAD, Polytechnic of Porto (ISEP/IPP) Porto, Portugal

Abstract:

Peer-to-peer electricity transactions inside local electricity communities have emerged based on the possibility for prosumers to transact electricity locally without the need for an intermediary [1][2]. To obtain the best solution in these models is necessary to implement optimization methods that determine the best transactions within the energy community. Particle Swarm Optimization is a good solution for this problem because it allows reaching results in a short optimization time. The adaptation to the problem becomes very simplified compared to some optimization tools available [3]. Thus, a sensitivity analysis of the different parameters that incorporate the Particle Swarm Optimization research process is proposed in this work. For the current study, the Particle Swarm Optimization algorithm will be used to optimize the peer-to-peer electricity market problem. Thus, a sensitivity analysis of the Particle Swarm Optimization parameters contributes to the algorithm's better behavior. Inertia term describes that the previous velocity influences the current velocity. Controlling its selection may tune the global and local search ability of Particle Swarm Optimization. Personal and global acceleration represent the particle stochastic acceleration weight toward the personal best and the global best. The number of iterations and particles influence the results because a greater number of them results in a better fitness value. But in problems where processing time is critical, a value that considers both metrics (fitness and time) should be chosen. The sensitive analyses are performed to obtain the best combination between the number of iterations, number of particles, inertia term, local coefficient, and global coefficient.

Related References:

- [1]- R. Faia, J. Soares, T. Pinto, F. Lezama, Z. Vale and J. M. Corchado, "Optimal Model for Local Energy Community Scheduling Considering Peer to Peer Electricity Transactions," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 12420-12430, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3051004.
- [2] - Faia, R., Lezama, F., & Corchado, J. M. (2021). Local electricity markets—practical implementations. In *Local Electricity Markets* (pp. 127-140). Academic Press.
- [3] - Faia, R., Faria, P., Vale, Z., & Spinola, J. (2019). Demand response optimization using particle swarm algorithm considering optimum battery energy storage schedule in a residential house. *Energies*, 12(9), 1645.